

Study of Haematological Profile of Children Diagnosed with Severe Acute Malnutrition

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Abstract

Background: Severe Acute Malnutrition continues to be a significant public health issue globally, especially in low- and middle-income nations. It is a life-threatening condition that plays a major role in childhood illness and death. Children with SAM are at heightened risk of infections, developmental delays, and poor health outcomes. Haematological parameters are crucial in understanding the extent of anemia, immune function, and overall health status in malnourished children, therefore understanding the hematological profile of children with SAM is essential for early diagnosis, effective treatment, and improved patient outcomes.

Aim: To study the haematological parameters in Severe Acute Malnourished children.

Objectives: To study the morphological spectrum of anemia, any WBC abnormality, or any other abnormal haematological parameters in severe acute malnutrition.

Methodology: This prospective observational study included 243 children from 6 months to 59 months of age with Severe Acute Malnutrition admitted in Department of Pediatric Medicine, fulfilling the diagnostic criteria for severe acute malnutrition. Venous blood sample was collected in pediatric ward by venipuncture and was sent to central laboratory for analysis.

Results: Anemia was the most common haematological abnormality, 92.2% of total 243 children suffering from SAM included in the study had Anemia. In the study, out of 224 children with anemia, 134(59.8%) had microcytic anemia, 49(21.9%) had normocytic anemia, and 41(18.3%) had macrocytic anemia. Leukocytosis was present in 67 (27.57%) of the total children, leukopenia was present in 20 (8.23%) children, thrombocytosis was present in 68 (27.98%) children and thrombocytopenia was present in 30 (12.35%) children of the total children with SAM.

Conclusion: This study concludes that the primary haematological abnormality in children diagnosed with severe acute malnutrition is anemia, followed by thrombocytosis and leukocytosis. Children with severe acute malnutrition often exhibit abnormal haematological parameters. As a result, it is crucial to closely monitor these parameters and adjust treatment protocols accordingly to manage infections and support quicker recovery.

Keywords: Severe acute malnutrition, SAM, Haematological Profile in SAM, Anemia in SAM.

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Introduction

Severe Acute Malnutrition (SAM) continues to be a significant public health issue globally, especially in low- and middle-income nations. It is a life-threatening condition that plays a major role in childhood illness and death. SAM is marked by severe wasting, indicated by a very low weight-for-height/length (below -3 z-scores of the WHO growth standards), and/or the presence of nutritional edema.[1] Children with SAM face a higher risk of infections, delayed physical and cognitive development, and an elevated risk of mortality.[2] The haematological profile of children with SAM can provide essential information about the physiological changes and complications associated with the condition. Blood parameters such as haemoglobin levels, red and white blood cell counts, and platelet counts reflect the body's response to malnutrition and its ability to

combat infections.[3] These parameters are vital for understanding the extent of anemia, immune function, and overall health in malnourished children. Malnutrition disrupts the balance of essential nutrients, impairing blood cell production and function. Anemia is a frequent complication in SAM, often caused by deficiencies in iron, vitamin B12 and folate.[2] Additionally, weakened immune function due to malnutrition can lead to abnormal white blood cell counts, increasing the risk of infections.[1] Platelet abnormalities can also occur, elevating the risk of bleeding and other complications.[4] Studying the haematological profile in children with SAM is crucial for several reasons: it aids in the early detection and treatment of haematological issues, improves prognosis, and provides insights into the pathophysiological mechanisms of SAM, guiding

more effective treatment strategies. Furthermore, it underscores the need for integrated care approaches that address both nutritional and haematological concerns.

Aim: To study the haematological parameters in Severe Acute Malnourished children.

Objectives

1. To study the morphological spectrum of anemia in patients diagnosed with Severe Acute Malnutrition.
2. To evaluate any associated WBC abnormality.
3. To observe and correlate any other abnormal haematological parameters.

Materials and Methods

This prospective observational study was done to study the haematological parameters in SAM children. The inclusion criteria for the study were children from 6 months to 59 months of age, diagnosed with Severe Acute Malnutrition admitted in Department of Pediatric Medicine. Diagnostic criteria for severe acute malnutrition were, very low weight-for-length/height (Z score below -3SD of the median WHO child growth standards) and/or Mid-upper arm circumference < 115 mm and/or Presence of Nutritional oedema. Exclusion criteria were, children below 6 months and over 59 months of age, not falling in the age criteria and children in the age criteria but not falling in the criteria for severe acute malnutrition. This study was done on 243 patients, in Jhalawar Medical College and Hospital, Jhalawar, Rajasthan who were diagnosed as children suffering from severe acute malnutrition. Venous blood sample was collected in pediatric ward by venipunctures in vacutainer containing K2 EDTA anticoagulant and was sent to central laboratory for analysis. The sample was run into automated 5-part CBC analyzer (Sysmex XN1000) which analyses the sample and provides a printout with complete blood count, RBC indices, RDW, platelet count, retic, scattergram, and distribution curves. Peripheral blood smears were prepared, made to visualize better morphology wherever required. Values of hemoglobin for Anemia according to age group was taken using criteria given by WHO. Children of age group 6–23 months having hemoglobin <10.5 g/dL and children of age group 24–59 months having hemoglobin <11.0 g/dL were categorized as children with anemia.[5] Grading of anemias for different age groups was done according to WHO criteria.

For age group 6–23 months: Mild grade anemia above 9.5 g/dL up to cut off limit, moderate grade anemia from 7 to 9.4 g/dl and severe grade anemia – less than 7 g/dl.[5]

For age group 24–59 months: Mild grade anemia above 10 g/dL up to cut off limit, moderate grade 7–9.9 g/dl and severe grade – less than 7 g/dl.[5]

Normal range for Total Leukocyte count for 6 months to 23 months of age: 6.0–14.0 cells ($\times 10^9/L$) and 4.0–12.0 cells ($\times 10^9/L$) for 24 months to 59 months age group.[6]

Normal range for platelet counts 150–400 $\times 10^9/L$. [6]

Results

There were 243 children diagnosed with SAM included in the study, out of which 118 (48.6%) were males and 125 (51.4%) were females. Total number of children in the age group of 6–23 months were 213 (87.65%), and 30 (12.35%) in the age group of 24–59 months (Table 1).

Table 1: Distribution of SAM children according to age groups.

Age group (months)	Numbers	Percentage (%)
6–23	213	87.65
24–59	30	12.35
Total	243	100

In this study the most common haematological abnormality was anemia as 92.2% of total children diagnosed with SAM also had anemia. 92.5% children of age group 6–23 months and 90% children of age group 24–59 months had anemia. Anemia was more prevalent in females in both the age groups that is, 97.22% of the total female children in the 6–23 months age group and 94.12% of total female children in the 24–59 months age group were anemic, whereas 87.62% and 84.61% of the total male children in the age group 6–23 months and 24–59 months respectively, were anemic.

Among the 243 children with SAM studied 24 (9.9%) of the children had mild anemia, 97 (39.9%) had moderate anemia, 103 (42.4%) had severe anemia and 19 (7.8%) of the children had no anemia, showing that severe anemia was the most common followed by moderate anemia and mild anemia (Table 2). Among the 224 children with anemia in the study 134 (59.8%) had microcytic anemia, 49 (21.9%) had normocytic anemia and 41 (18.3%) had macrocytic anemia (Table 3).

Among other haematological abnormalities in children with SAM, thrombocytosis and leukocytosis were the next common after anemia. Thrombocytosis was seen in 68 (27.98%) of the total children and leukocytosis was seen in 67 (27.57%) of the total children with SAM in this study. 12.35% of the total children with SAM had thrombocytopenia and 8.23% had leukopenia in this study (Table 4).

Table 2: Distribution according to Severity of Anemia

Severity of Anemia	Age group (6–23 months)	Age group (24–59 months)	Total	Percentage
Mild	22	2	24	9.9
Moderate	83	14	97	39.9
Severe	92	11	103	42.4
No Anemia	16	3	19	7.8
Total	213	30	243	100

Table 3: Distribution of SAM children with anemia according to Type of anemia

Type of Anemia	Frequencies	Percentage
Microcytic	134	59.8
Normocytic	49	21.9
Macrocytic	41	18.3
Total	224	100

Table 4: Distribution of Haematological Abnormalities in SAM

Haematological Abnormalities	Frequencies	Percentage
Anemia	224	92.18
Leukocytosis	67	27.57
Leukopenia	20	8.23
Thrombocytosis	68	27.98
Thrombocytopenia	30	12.35

Figure 1: Distribution of Haematological Abnormalities in SAM

Anemia was significantly more prevalent in female children with severe acute malnutrition (SAM) than in males (96.8% of total females and 87.3% of total males with SAM had anemia). However, the distribution of anemia was nearly identical across both age groups (6–23 months and 24–59 months), with 92.5% and 90% of children experiencing anemia, respectively.

Leukocytosis was similarly distributed among both genders, with a slight predominance in male children (28.8%) than female children (26.4%). Older children (24–59 months) exhibited a higher prevalence of leukocytosis (46.7%) compared to younger children (6–23 months, 24.9%).

In this study the mean reticulocyte percentage among children with severe acute malnutrition was 1.5%, falling within the normal range.

Discussion

In this study, children aged 6–23 months represented the majority of those diagnosed with severe acute malnutrition (SAM), accounting for 87.65% of the total SAM cases. A similar study by Getawa et al. [7] found that 60.2% of children with SAM fell within the 6–23 months age group.

Haematological parameters in children with SAM often show significant alterations, as indicated by various studies. These changes are believed to stem

from factors such as nutritional deficiencies, disruptions in bone marrow haematopoiesis, alterations in haematopoietic progenitor cell cycles [8], and variations in colony-stimulating factor production by macrophages. [7,9] As also seen in this study, majority of the children diagnosed with SAM also had anemia. Along with anemia, leukocytosis and thrombocytosis was also frequently seen.

Anemia was the most common haematological abnormality observed in this study, affecting 92.2% of the SAM children. This aligns with findings from other studies, such as one by Arya AK et al. [10], where 95% of children with SAM were found to have anemia, and another by Dwivedi D et al. [11], where 85% of children had anemia. A study by Naina Rose et al. [12] reported anemia in 87% of children with SAM.

Among the 224 SAM children with anemia in this study, severe anemia was the most prevalent, affecting 45.98%, followed by moderate anemia (43.30%) and mild anemia (10.71%). This distribution is consistent with other studies, including one by Naina Rose et al. [12], where 51.9% of the anemic children had severe anemia, 33.8% had moderate anemia, and 14.3% had mild anemia.

Microcytic anemia was the most common type of anemia in this study, affecting 59.8% of the anemic children, followed by normocytic anemia (21.9%) and macrocytic anemia (18.3%). In a similar study done by Getawa et al. [7], it was found that 73.1% of children with SAM had microcytic anemia and 25.4% had normocytic anemia. Whereas Dwivedi D et al. [11] found that macrocytic anemia was the most prevalent type in their study. The high prevalence of microcytic anemia in malnourished children in this study may be attributed to iron deficiency, depletion of iron stores and inadequate consumption of iron rich foods in the surrounding local region.

Leukocytosis was observed in 27.57% of the SAM children in this study, which is consistent with the 26.7% prevalence found by Getawa et al. [7]. Other studies also report leukocytosis as a common feature among malnourished children. Leukocytosis is often linked to increased infections, such as gastroenteritis and respiratory tract infections, which are common in children with severe acute malnutrition.

Leukopenia, on the other hand, was found in 8.23% of the SAM children in this study. In Dwivedi D et al.'s study [11], 9% of children with SAM had leukopenia. Leukopenia may be contributed due to the deficiency of vitamin B12 in patients with SAM. [11]

Thrombocytosis was observed in 27.98% of the children with SAM in this study, which is in line with findings from other studies [13,14] that indicate thrombocytosis as a common feature in children with severe acute malnutrition. Increased platelet

counts in SAM children may be associated with frequent infections, which trigger inflammatory cytokines that stimulate platelet production. [15]

In this study, thrombocytopenia was seen in 12.35% of the SAM children. Low platelet counts in children diagnosed with severe acute malnutrition was also seen in other studies [10,16]. In SAM children, thrombocytopenia may result from reduced bone marrow activity due to nutritional deficiencies and/or from platelet destruction due to infections. [10,16]

Conclusion

This study found that anemia was the most common type of hematological abnormality among children with severe acute malnutrition, severe anemia followed by moderate and mild anemia. Thrombocytosis and leukocytosis were next following anemia. These findings highlight the importance of monitoring not only hemoglobin levels but also platelet and white blood cell counts in this population. Abnormalities in these parameters can indicate underlying infections and may guide more effective treatment strategies for SAM. Given the high prevalence of hematological abnormalities in children with severe acute malnutrition, it is crucial to prioritize hematological assessments and adjust treatment protocols accordingly to facilitate faster recovery. To further reduce the burden of severe acute malnutrition, comprehensive interventions such as deworming programs, food fortification, malnutrition prevention initiatives, and public awareness campaigns are essential.

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